

IMPLICATIONS OF VIOLENCE ON INI LOCAL GOVERNMENT AREA OF AKWA IBOM STATE, NIGERIA

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ABSTRACT

Violence as a result of conflict is becoming visible characteristics of Nigerian communities in recent times. The effects are vast affecting the nation's economic planning, which has generated several implications on the lives and socio-economic situations of Nigerians. This study examined violence and its implications on Ini Local Government area of Akwa Ibom State. The study sought to ascertain the extent which violence affects income distribution and land distribution in Ini Local Government area of Akwa Ibom State. Conflict Theory was adopted by the researchers for theoretical framework. Two research hypotheses were tested at 0.05 level of significant. Krejice and Morgan's model of sample was employed to select 384 participants. Out of 384 respondents that received the questionnaire, only 350 returned their questionnaire which was used for the analysis. Multi-stage sampling technique was used to draw sample from each selected community. Data for this study were collected using structured questionnaire entitled "Violence Measurement Questionnaire (VMQ) with 24 items and Socio-economic Development Questionnaire with 20 items". Simple linear regression statistic was used in testing the hypotheses at 0.05 level of significant. The findings revealed that violence significantly affects income distribution and land distribution in Ini Local development and Government Area. This implies that violence has adversely affected on the lives and socio-economic condition of Ini people. It was recommended among other things that the government should address the issue of economic and social problem associated with poverty, corruption, illiteracy, youth unemployment and marginalization.

KEYWORDS: Violence, conflict, income, land distribution and Ini people

INTRODUCTION

Violence is a common decimal in every society or state. This occurs as certain group of people perceived injustice, unfairness and inequality. The reaction to injustice and

deprivation is what is seen as violence. According to Lawal (2010) violence is the intentional use of physical force or power, threatened or actual, against oneself, another person, or against a group or community, which either results in or has a high likelihood of resulting in injury, death, psychological harm, mal development or deprivation. This invariably has affected the peaceful co-existence and leads to social unrest as well as socio-economic malady. Violence is common and unavoidable in all human society. All over the world, violence and conflicts occur because society is made up of people with differing interests and values (Willie *et al.*, 2021).. In most societies, it occurs when parties in a state of independence perceives divergent views or believe that their aspirations or goals cannot be achieved simultaneously.. Therefore, it is only natural that where there is inequality in access to the control of natural resources and political power for instance, there would be discontent, opposition and controversy.

A number of violent conflicts have erupted in both developed and developing countries, inflicting sufferings and pains on the people and placing enormous stress on the environment (Gyabaah, 2006). These include political, communal, unemployment based, organized violence group and others. In Nigeria, politics has remained the central factor in conflict and violent. The electoral politics in Nigeria right from 1960s till date has been characterized with violent conflicts, political thuggery, assassinations, and arson. Politicians in Nigeria do not accommodate dialogue, negotiation and consensus (Eme and Onyishi, 2011). Political contests are characterized by desperation, and violent struggle for political power among politicians. Recurring political violence in Nigeria could be attributed to over-zealousness and desperation of political gladiators to win elections or remain in office at all cost. These misadventures have often been catastrophic leading to decimation of innocent lives, disruption of economic activities, and the destruction of properties among others.

Communal conflict is a social conflict that relates to a group or groups in a society. When it occurs within a group, it is known as intra-communal conflict and inter-communal conflict when it occurs between groups. Communal violence (sometimes inter-communal violence) is a situation where violence is perpetuated across ethnic lines, and victims are chosen based upon ethnic group membership (Horowitz, 2000). Dzurgba (2006) has posited that communal violence is that which occurs between two or more communities over territorial land, farmland and territorial water for fishing. Therefore, communal conflict is a state of incompatibility that emanates from a commonly shared or used property or resource by a group or groups in a society. It occurs within or between groups that are defined by some forms of social ties over resources that are jointly owned or shared in a community. This conflict often leads to loss of lives and properties, as well as other valuable resources. Unemployment based violence among Nigerians, especially the youths is a major cause of violent crimes in Nigeria (Adagba, *et al.*, 2012). In particular, youth's unemployment has contributed to the rising cases of violent conflict in Nigeria. Also, one of the major causes of violent in the country is the failure of successive administration to address challenges of poverty, unemployment, and inequitable distribution of wealth among ethnic nationalities.

Organised violence groups such as ethnic militia, vigilantes, secret cults in tertiary institutions and political thugs contribute significantly to violent challenges in Nigeria in different dimension and forms. Their emergence have been linked to a number of factors which include the culture of militarism that has its antecedents in military rule, the failure of the state and its institutions, economic disempowerment, the structure of the state and

Nigeria's federalism, non-separation of state and religion, politics of exclusion, culture of patriarchy, ignorance and poor political consciousness (Eme and Onyishi, 2011).

Economic development generally refers to the sustained, concerted actions of policy makers and communities that promote the standard of living and economic health of a specific area. Economic development can also be referred to the quantitative and qualitative changes in the economy. Such actions can involve multiple development of human capital, critical infrastructure in lagging areas, regional competitiveness, environmental sustainability, social inclusion, health, safety, literacy and other initiatives. Socio-economic development is a product of development and can be defined as the process of social and economic transformation in a society. Socio-economic development embraces changes taking place in the social sphere mostly of an economic nature. Thus, socio-economic development is made up of processes caused by exogenous and endogenous factors which determine the course and direction of the development. It is measured with indicators, such as GDP, life expectancy, literacy and levels of employment. Changes in less-tangible factors are also considered, such as personal dignity, freedom of association, personal safety and freedom from fear of physical harm, and the extent of participation in civil society. Causes of socio-economic impacts are, for example, new technologies, changes in laws, changes in the physical environment and ecological changes. Economic inequality is also a major factor that contributes to violent in Nigeria as it is in Ini Local Government Area. There is a general perception of marginalization by a section of the people in such areas as government development policies and political patronage, and these trigger disaffection, resentment, and revolt (Achumba, *et al.*, 2013). The incessant strikes by labour, professional groups and demonstrations by civil society groups are mainly due to pervasive material inequalities and unfairness. Their agitations are aimed at drawing public sympathy for their struggle for just and fair treatment by the government.

Land inequality is a major factor in the evolution of economic inequality as it is the ultimate storage of wealth in pre-industrial societies (Easterly and Levine 2003). Since land usually depreciates at a slower pace than most other forms of human, physical and natural capital its value can be easily passed on from one generation to the next. Any country, state or local government with natural endowments (soil, climate) suitable to growing scale intensive cash crops are, therefore, likely to end up with higher levels of land inequality, *ceteris paribus*. Land is unequally distributed in Ini Local Government Area among the people and there is both efficiency and a social equity case of land reform. Land reform has been repeatedly blocked by political power with obnoxious motive for large plantation and estate development. Inequality in the distribution of assets such as land is likely to be more persistent in a context of concentrated political power. If the political and landowning elite are largely overlapping the elite may devise policies that suppress democratic accountability and social development in order to maintain the distributional status quo (Acemoglu and Robinson 2006).

Scholars have identified strong links between security and development since the cold war ended (Nwanegbo and Odigbo, 2013; Chandler, 2007). They argued that development cannot be achieved in any nation where there are conflicts, crisis and war. There is a consensus in the literature that security and development are two different and inseparable concepts that affect each other, and this has naturally triggered debates on security-development nexus (Chandler, 2007; Stan 2004). Violence in Ini Local Government

has complex historical roots. Historical stratification in wealth and land ownership contributes to economic grievances. Weak property rights and lack of access to justice has created a climate in which disagreements cannot be reliably settled via official means, leading people to take the law into their own hands.

Income is unequally distributed in Ini Local Government Area. Inequality in income distribution has not only produced social strains, but also ultimately retard development. The bulk of benefits go to the middle classes (politicians and its stakeholders) and the rich. The unequal distribution of social spending is no doubt a major factor in maintaining inequality and thus poverty set in. Income inequality affects the pace at which growth enables poverty reduction (Ravallion 2004). Widening income inequality is the defining challenge of our time. In advanced economies, the gap between the rich and poor is at its highest level in decades. Inequality trends have been more mixed in Emerging Markets and Developing Countries (EMDCs), with some countries experiencing declining inequality, but pervasive inequities in access to education, health care, and finance remain. Extreme inequality may damage trust and social cohesion and thus is also associated with conflicts, which discourage investment. Conflicts are particularly prevalent in the management of common resources (Bardhan, 2005).

Another dimension of violence is the quest for political position in Ini Local Government Area of Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria, political domineering by a section of the local government and uneven distribution of economic resources among various communities. More violent emanates as a result of lop-sidedness in indices of socio-economic development such as unemployment, poverty, poor economic growth, lack of comprehensive basic infrastructure such as good road network, water supply, electricity, and industry. It may be possible that politics, communal conflicts, organized group or unemployment can affect socio-economic development. The economic development under investigation includes income distribution, land distribution, infrastructural development and educational development. Therefore, the researchers were interested in investigating violence and its implications on socio-economic development of Ini Local Government Area.

REVIEW OF RELATED LITERATURE

Concept of violence

Violence is the intentional use of physical force or power, threatened or actual, against oneself, another person, or against a group or community that either results in or has a high likelihood of resulting in injury, death, psychological harm, mal development or deprivation (Handley, 2010). It was stressed that at the heart of many of these conflicts is access to resources and control over the distribution of benefits. This struggle for resources has led to a broad sense of insecurity, opportunism, and the pursuit of self-help strategies across the country. Violence is defined by the World Health Organization (WHO) as the international use of physical force of power, threatened or actual against oneself, another person, or against a group or community, that either results in or has a high likelihood of resulting in injuries, death psychological harm, mal development or deprivation (WHO, 2016).

Some Nigerians argue that the real reason for the violence is not ethnic or religious differences but the scramble for land, scarce resources and political clout. Poverty,

joblessness and corrupt politics drive extremists from both sides to commit horrendous atrocities. Although the nation rakes in billions of dollars in oil revenue annually, the majority of Nigerians live with less than a dollar a day. Some of the major security problems currently confronting the nation have been identified to include: political and electioneering conflicts, socio-economic agitations, ethno-religious crises, ethnic militias, boundary disputes, cultism, criminality and organised crimes. These problems individually and collectively constitute threats to the peace, security and development of the country (Lawal, 2010).

Violent conflict is arguably one of the most important challenges facing the world today. The incidence of international and civil wars has decreased in recent years (Harbom and Wallensteen 2009), but the legacy of violence persists in many countries, affecting the effectiveness of global development, international peace and democracy-building processes worldwide, as well as disrupting the living conditions of local populations, often for generations (Okoro *et al*, 2023). Yet, we have limited rigorous evidence of how people live in contexts of conflict: what choices they make, how institutional arrangements impact on and are affected by these decisions, and what policies may work in strengthening peace and post-conflict development processes. This lack of systematic understanding of the interplay between violent conflict and development has limited the effectiveness of policy interventions, and weakened processes of state- and peace-building in areas affected by conflict and violence. For a long time, research on the causes of violent conflict focused on the mediation and resolution of conflicting interests between governments and opposing groups, while studies on its consequences have concentrated on estimating the costs that wars impose on countries (Hirshleifer, 2001).

Government at the Federal, State or Local Government has a prime duty of providing security and welfare to the people. Unfortunately, government on this constitutional responsibility has failed to provide a secured and safe environment for lives, properties and the conduct of business and economic activities. The alarming level of violent in Nigeria has fuelled the crime rate and terrorists attacks in different parts of the country, leaving unpalatable consequences for the nation's economy and its growth. To address the threat to national security and combat the increasing waves of crime, the Federal Government in the 2013 budget made a huge allocation to security, and the national assembly passed the Anti-Terrorism Act in 2011 (Ewetan, 2013). Despite these efforts, the level of violent and insecurity in the country is still high, and a confirmation of this is the low ranking of Nigeria in the Global Peace Index (GPI, 2012). Similarly, the plethora of security measures taken to address the daunting challenges of violent in Nigeria, government efforts have not produced the desired positive result. This has compelled the Nigerian government in recent time to request for foreign assistance from countries such as USA, Israel, and EU countries to combat the rising waves of terrorism and violent. Amidst the deteriorating security situation in the country, Nigeria is also confronted with daunting developmental challenges which pose serious threat to socio-economic development. These developmental challenges include endemic rural and urban poverty, high rate of unemployment, debilitating youth unemployment, low industrial output, unstable and deteriorating exchange rate, high inflation rate, inadequate physical and social infrastructure, very large domestic debt, and rising stock of external debt (Ewetan, 2013). Development is a multifaceted phenomenon and man centered. It is the process of empowering people to maximize their potentials, and

develop the knowledge capacity to exploit nature to meet daily human needs (Ake, 2001). The transformation of the society and the emergence of new social and economic organizations are critical indicators of development (Nwanegbo and Odigbo, 2013).

Violence and its implication on income distribution

Inequality in income distribution has not only produced social strains, but also ultimately retard development. The bulk of benefits go to the middle classes (politicians and its stakeholders) and the rich. The unequal distribution of social spending is no doubt a major factor in maintaining inequality and thus poverty set in. Income inequality affects the pace at which growth enables poverty reduction (Ravallion 2004). Widening income inequality is the defining challenge of our time. In advanced economies, the gap between the rich and poor is at its highest level in decades. Inequality trends have been more mixed in Emerging Markets and Developing Countries (EMDCs), with some countries experiencing declining inequality, but pervasive inequities in access to education, health care, and finance remain. Extreme inequality may damage trust and social cohesion and thus is also associated with conflicts, which discourage investment. Conflicts are particularly prevalent in the management of common resources (Bardhan, 2005).

Jolley *et al.*, (2012) argue that place- based strategies overlooked the systematic factors which perpetuate poverty, such as disparate access to quality education, employment opportunities, and the psychological and social effects of living in low income areas. People based economic development focuses on developing human capital of poor, low skilled individuals and increasing individual capability to compete in, and access formal labour markets. This may occur through education programmes or skills training, transportation assistance to places of employment, or transfer payments and subsidies that enable them to leave their communities.

Violence is assuming dangerous tendencies as they threaten life, property, the national sense of well-being, peace, security, social order and eventually, reducing the citizens' quality of life (Agbola, 2004). The concern now is that violence can have strong negative impacts on economic development by drastically reducing growth and producing long-lasting detrimental social impacts at macro and micro economy levels (World Bank, 2009). The impact of violence on the economy is substantial, because it generates great costs to society at different levels, from individual to national. The environmental, social health and economic ramifications of this situation in society has a tremendous impact on the economy and security (Ogboi, 2009).

Many sociological explanations of crime had proffered that economic deprivation acts as a motivational factor in the manifestation of crime. While the causal role that economic hardship plays in promoting criminal behaviour differs, most explanations had advanced some variant of the basic theme that poverty in a stratified society weakens institutional legitimacy and undermines the social bonds between these institutions and the impoverished. Economic hardship had been deemed especially critical in grasping an understanding of the disparity evinced frequently between the crime rates of Blacks and Whites in the United States, given that Blacks, on average, live in conditions that are much more economically barren than Whites (Wilson, 2007).

Following the logic articulated in the seminal work by Blau and Blau (2002) social scientists had commonly examined whether racial disparities in socio-economic conditions

influenced racial differences in crime rates. Indeed, Blau and Blau (2002) argued rather cogently that economic inequality, or the unequal distribution of wealth, money, and other economic resources between racial groups, had greater salience in explaining crime rates than the absolute level of socioeconomic conditions for a given racial group. It is theorized that economic inequality engenders resentment, hostility, frustration, and to be a precipitating factor in the impetus of criminal behavior (Blau and Blau, 2002) or more recently, as an indicator of the relative disadvantage that Blacks face in competing with Whites for scarce jobs and other resources (Jacobs and Wood, 2009).

Despite great interest and intuitive appeal, research to date had been unable to provide unwavering support for the thesis that economic inequality between racial groups, or interracial economic inequality, accounted for racial differences in crime rates. While a few early research studies lent support to the interracial economic inequality thesis (Blau and Golden, 2006; Blau and Schwartz, 2004), other more contemporary research efforts had failed to adduce convincing evidence of a relationship between economic inequality and crime (Harer and Steffensmeier, 2002; Messner and Golden, 2002). These recent failures to uncover support for the interracial economic inequality thesis has led to alternative conceptualizations of economic inequality, particularly the notion that intra racial economic inequality may be more salient in predicting group crime rates than inter racial inequality (Phillips, 2007). Saheed and Egwaikhide (2012) found out that political violence leads to wanton destruction of properties, waste of resources, and hence inefficient utilization of resources. Acemoglu and Robinson (2006) posited that if the political and landowning elite are largely overlapping the elites may devise policies that suppress democratic accountability and social development in order to maintain the distributional status quo. Oboh and Hyande (2006) also reported that communal conflict as involving two or more communities engaging themselves in disagreement or act of violence over issues such as claims for land ownership, religious and political difference leading to loss of lives and destruction of properties. Ikurekong *et al.*, (2012) found out that communal conflicts in quest for land ownership have become a plague that has eaten deep into the fabric of Nigerian economy.

THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK

Conflict Theory

Conflict theory is theory propounded by Karl Marx in 1971 that claims that society is in a state of perpetual conflict due to competition for limited resources. Conflict theory holds that social order is maintained by domination and power, rather than consensus and conformity. According to conflict theory, those with wealth and power try to hold on to it by any means possible, chiefly by suppressing the poor and powerless. Conflict theorist argues that individuals and groups (social classes) within society have differing amounts and of material and non-material resources such as wealthy versus poor and that the more powerful groups use their power in order to exploit groups with less power. Conflict theory states that tensions and conflicts arise when resources, status, and power are unevenly distributed between groups in society, and that these conflicts become the engine for social change. In this context, power can be understood as control of politics and institutions that make up society, and one's social status relative to others determined not just by class but by race, gender, sexuality, culture and religion, among other things.

In sociology, conflict theory states that society or an organization functions so that each individual participant and its groups struggle to maximize their benefits, which inevitably contributes to social change such as political changes and revolutions. However the activities of citizens aimed at maintaining the resistance leads to increased escalation of political violence in Nigeria. In Ini Local Government Area of Akwa Ibom State, violence as a social conflict has been influence by various factors which are socio-economically related. These violence activities do affect different aspects of the people's life which the influence is what this research work is aimed at investigating.

METHODOLOGY

The research design employed in this study was survey design. Survey design typically employs questionnaires or interviews in order to determine the opinions, attitudes, preferences, and perceptions of persons of interest to the researcher (Udoh and Joseph, 2005). The study was carried out in Ini Local Government Area of Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria. The Local Government Area was carved out of the former Ikono Local Government Area in 1991. The population of the study is 99,196 made up of 52,644 males and 46,552 females (NPC, 2006). This represents the population in the 27 communities in Ini Local Government Area.

Three hundred and fifty one (384) people were used in the study. This sample was obtained using Krejice and Morgan's (1970) model sample of size determination. The multi-stage sampling procedure was employed in selecting samples. First, each of sample community forms a cluster. In each community, sub-clustering unit was form from organised association such as youth association, women association, farmers' association, sand dealers association, business associations, age group association and Labour unions. On the basis of this arrangement respondents were selected using simple random sampling technique. This technique gives each member of the cluster independent and equal chance to be selected. And from each cluster thirty nine (39) respondents were selected.

Instrument used for data collection was tagged Violence Measurement Questionnaire (VMQ)' and 'Socio-economic Development Questionnaire (SDQ)' were used in the study. VMQ had 24 items measured on a-5 point rating scale of Very High Extent (VHE), High Extent (HE), Moderate Extent (ME), Little Extent (LE) and Very Little Extent (VLE), while SDQ had 16 items measured on a-4 point rating scale of Very Good (VG), Good (G), Fair (F), and Poor (P). Data were analysed through simple descriptive statistics such inferential statistics of simple linear regression which was used to test the null hypotheses at .05 level of significance.

RESULTS

Ho₁: Violence does not significantly affect income distribution in Ini Local Government Area.

The hypothesis was tested at 0.05 level of significant and the result presented in Table 1.

Table 1: **Result of simple linear regression analysis of the effect of violence on income distribution in the L.G.A**

Model	Sum of squares	Df	Mean Square	F-cal	F-crit
Regression	1786.655	1	1786.655	21.87*	3.86
Residual	28013.907	349	81.673		
Total	29800.562	350			

*Significant at .05 alpha level

The result in Table 1 shows that the calculated F-value of 21.87 is greater than the critical F-value of 3.86 at .05 level of significance with 1 and 349 degrees of freedom. The result is significant; therefore the null hypothesis that violence does not significantly affect income distribution in Ini Local Government Area is rejected. This result implies that violence significantly affect income distribution in Ini Local Government Area,

Ho₂: Violence does not significantly affect land distribution in Ini Local Government Area.

The hypothesis was tested at 0.05 level of significant and the result presented in Table 2.

Table 2: Result of simple linear regression analysis of the effect of violence on land distribution in Ini L.G.A.

Model	Sum of squares	Df	Mean Square	F-cal	F-crit
Regression	1977.045	1	1786.655	21.87*	3.86
Residual	27823.517	349	81.673		
Total	29800.562	350			

*Significant at .05 alpha level

The result in Table 6 shows that the calculated F-value of 21.87 is greater than the critical F-value of 3.86 at .05 level of significance with 1 and 349 degrees of freedom. The result is significant; therefore the null hypothesis that violence does not significantly affect land distribution in Ini Local Government Area is rejected. This result implies that violence significantly affect land distribution in Ini Local Government Area.

DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

The findings of this study have been organized and discussed according to the three research questions posed and the three hypotheses formulated to guide the study. The research questions were discussed first followed by the hypotheses as outlined below.

Violence and its implication on income distribution

Data as presented in Table 1 provides answers to research question one. The findings revealed that violence affects income distribution. The R-value was .692 and R² value of 0.479 revealed that violent affects income distribution 47.9%. The analysis of hypothesis 1 in Table 5 shows that the calculated F-value of 21.87 was greater than the critical F-value of 3.86 at 0.05 alpha level and 1 and 349 degrees of freedom. The deduction from Table 1 is that violence affects income distribution in Ini L.G.A. With this observation, the null hypothesis which assumed that Violence does not significantly affect income distribution in Ini Local Government Area is rejected.

The finding of this study agrees with the view of Ravallion (2004) who opined that inequality in income distribution has not only produced social strains, but also ultimately

retard development. The bulk of benefits go to the middle classes (politicians and its stakeholders) and the rich. The unequal distribution of social spending is no doubt a major factor in maintaining inequality and thus poverty set in. Income inequality affects the pace at which growth enables poverty reduction. Nwanegbo and Odigbo (2013) argued that development cannot be achieved in any nation where there are conflicts, crisis and war. Saheed and Egwaikhide (2012) found out that political violence leads to wanton destruction of properties, waste of resources, and hence inefficient utilization of resources

Violence and its implication on land distribution

Data as presented in Table 2 provides answers to research question two. The findings revealed that violence affects land distribution in Ini L.G.A. The R-value was .701 and R2 value of 0.491 revealed that violent affects income distribution 49.1%. The analysis of hypothesis 2 in Table 6 shows that the calculated F-value of 24.37 was greater than the critical F-value of 3.86 at 0.05 alpha level and 1 and 349 degrees of freedom. The deduction from Table 6 is that violence affects land distribution in Ini L.G.A. With this observation, the null hypothesis which assumed that Violence does not significantly affect land distribution in Ini Local Government Area is rejected.

The finding of this study agrees with the report of Easterly and Levine (2003) that land inequality is a major factor in the evolution of economic inequality as it is the ultimate storage of wealth in pre-industrial societies. Acemoglu and Robinson (2006) posited that if the political and landowning elite are largely overlapping the elites may devise policies that suppress democratic accountability and social development in order to maintain the distributional status quo. Oboh and Hyande (2006) also reported that communal conflict as involving two or more communities engaging themselves in disagreement or act of violence over issues such as claims for land ownership, religious and political difference leading to loss of lives and destruction of properties. Ikurekong *et al.*, (2012) found out that communal conflicts in quest for land ownership have become a plague that has eaten deep into the fabric of Nigerian economy.

CONCLUSION

It has been established that Ini Local Government Area is blessed with abundant natural and human resources. However, these resources are wasted through the destruction of lives and properties resulting from political violence, communal conflict, unemployment and organised violence group. Political violence manifest in acrimony, assault, assassination, intimidation, harassment, maiming and killing consequently these affect the existing social relationship in the society. Communal conflict aggressively affects food production in the study area. This factor indicates that people, goods and services were often restricted during conflict period. This manifests in high vicious cycle of poverty among households in the period of conflict. As the socioeconomic life of the people is disrupted, widespread hunger, starvation and malnutrition remains a direct and common feature in conflict areas, than non- conflict areas. All these factors have led to the inability of the government to bridge the gap between the abundant resources and what is available to the citizens, and thereby constitute hindrance to the growth and development of economic growth in Ini Local Government Area which should provide good life.

RECOMMENDATIONS

In the light of the findings and conclusion drawn in this study, the following recommendations are made:

1. There is the need to focus on economic development in Nigeria vis-à-vis Ini Local Government Area to reduce violence.
2. There is a need to redirect the energies of our youths from crime, cultism and other vices towards more useful pursuits and other practical endeavours, which teach the dignity of labour, integrity and national services.
3. The government must address the issue of economic and social problem associated with poverty, corruption, illiteracy, youth unemployment and marginalization.
4. Nigerians should be educated and enlightened on the need to develop and promote the culture of peace because small arms bring devastation, exacerbate conflict, spark refugees flow, undermine the rule of law and spawn a culture of violence and impunity.
5. There is need for effective resource development, boundary dispute and food scarcity should be accorded greater priority and attention by policy makers.

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